

النظام الالى المتكامل يونيكورن وتطبيقه بمكتبة مبارك العامه : دراسة تقييمية

المستخلص

This study aimed to analyze and evaluate the Unicorn used in Mubarak public library with its various aspects in terms of its location between other automated systems in Arab libraries and analyzed in terms of its environment, components, search and retrieval features in addition to evaluated its using in the library with respect to the acquisition, technical operation, information services, administrative activities, and evaluation of user's interactive with it. Therefore, the study try to answer the following questions: -

- 1) What is the location of the Unicorn on the map of automated systems used in libraries and information centers .
- 2) What are the system requirements in terms of hardware and operating systems?
- 3) What are the components of the system and the possibility of search and retrieval in?
- 4) What is the efficiency of the system in the conduct of various office operations?
- 5) What is the capacity of systems to meet the needs of the beneficiaries?
- 6) The compatibility of the system with the provisions of the international standards for mechanical systems?

The Researcher used a method of case study for study of a particular system Unicorn, which has been applied in

Chapter I: about development of automated systems and integrated site unicorn among them.

Chapter II :about the use of the Unicorn in Mubarak Public Library.

Chapter III :about evaluation of the Unicorn integrated library system.

Chapter IV :about Unicorn evaluation from the point of user's view